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How to Win a Claim Arising Out of a Fume Event

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Abstract

This is the story of the first case to prove that the toxic fumes resulting from a fume event can cause permanent neurological damage. The Oregon attorney who won this case describes how he proved this case, and how he had overcome the industry response. The case was proven through the analogy of four links of a chain: factual, scientific, medical and disability. Each link is proven independently, and each link assumes the veracity of the other links. The factual link involves proving that the fume event did happen. The scientific link establishes that these fumes can cause these conditions. Assuming the first two links are proven, the medical link establishes that the pilot's conditions were likely caused by the fume event. The final link proves the resultant impairment. This concept defeated the industry argument that the scientists need to have read the entire medical record to offer an opinion, or that the doctors have to be able to defend the science. The links are independent. Therefore, the doctors are not deferring to the toxicologists. Other arguments included the industry assertion that without knowing the exact dose and composition of the fumes one cannot prove causation and that the only harmful component is the tri-ortho isomer. Scientific testimony established the other components of these fumes are harmful aside from the ortho isomer, and that causation can be proven without knowing the exact dose. The end result was an order from the court establishing that these toxic fumes caused a wide variety of neurological disabilities suffered by the pilot.

Keywords

fume event, OPIDN, legal case, compensation claim, strategy

1 Introduction

About four years ago a commercial pilot for Jet Blue was exposed to a fume event that produced severe injuries. He filed a worker's compensation claim in the State of Oregon. His claim was denied. The appeal of that denial went to trial. The judge overturned the denial and ruled in favor of the pilot.

This was the first case in North America or Europe to establish that these toxic fumes can cause permanent neurological impairment. The attorney who handled this case is a sole practitioner in Oregon who took on the airline industry and won. This is his presentation in which he describes this epic battle, the steps he had to take to prove this case, and the many obstacles he had to overcome to win.

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I have the unenviable task of summarizing 30 months of litigation into a few pages of a paper 30 minutes, so I will have to leave out most of the humorous anecdotes. And, since I want this to be both entertaining and useful, I will leave out all of the procedural shenanigans that are unique to Oregon Worker's Compensation Law.

Instead, *I will focus on two things: how to prove your case, and, how to defend the castle.* Since we can anticipate what attacks the industry will mount, you can set up your case in such a way as to allow yourself to fend off those attacks. Before we cover that, allow me to set the stage for you.

2 Captain Kirk Myers

Captain Kirk Myers was a Pilot for Jet Blue with over 20 years of experience. He was unfortunately subjected to a rather severe fume event about 4 years ago. When he arrived at Portland International Airport to begin his day, he was advised that the plane he was scheduled to fly had reported a bad smell on its previous flight. He and the FO were directed to spool up the engines while maintenance tried to figure it out.

During three separate 15 minute run ups they were subjected to very bad fumes. This produced immediate and severe symptoms including gagging, twitching and confusion. They were barely able to get off the plane. While the FO quickly recovered, Kirk's symptoms persisted. He called the company doctor that night and was told that he would be just fine. Just take some aspirin, drink some water and get some fresh air. The next morning Kirk thought he felt ok and when they flew to New York that day the FO handled the stick and Kirk handled the radio. Kirk's symptoms unfortunately then ramped up, and that was the last time that he ever flew. He has been disabled ever since.

He filed a worker's compensation claim that was initially vaguely accepted. The insurance company then tried to force him to settle out. When he refused, he and his Portland attorney parted ways, and the insurance company punished him by denying everything and shutting down the claim. Kirk then hired me with the marching orders: win the damn case.

Now, there is a certain sense of clarity that this brings. Knowing that there would be NO settlement meant that no matter how hard things got, there would be no easy bail out with a settlement. This would be a fight to the death. Either go big or go home.

3 The Oregon Attorney

I'm a sole practitioner in a tiny town in the mountains of Oregon. My entire legal team consists of me, my secretary, and my dog Mariposa. I'm taking on AIG Insurances Company and the airline industry. Not surprisingly, they were represented by probably one the largest and best defense firms in our state led by one of their best trial attorneys. What on earth was I thinking? I could just imagine the snickering in the Board Rooms back East: "Why we'll crush this hayseed." I love it when people underestimate me. What they didn't expect is that I'm a Chicago boy, born and raised. There, you learn the lesson, to use the words of Sean Connery in *The Untouchables*: "You don't bring a knife to a gunfight."

4 That's What You Have to Do: Overwhelm Them!

So, in my trial they bring in two doctors to say that my client is faking, and I counter with seven doctors to say he isn't. They bring in their hired gun from Seattle and I counter with Dr. Abou Donia, Dr. Kannecki, and Dr. Harrison. They assert that we don't really know what happen that day—or if there even was a fume event at all, and I fly in Dr. Michaelis to explain to the court exactly what happened that day. They deride us about the research in their opening statement: "Gee, Dr. Harrison says he has read over a hundred papers, well where are they, how do we really know what they say?" So I counter on day two of trial by wheeling in a hand truck with bankers boxes for the me, the judge and opposing counsel, containing in chronological order over 120 scientific studies and papers from the 1940s to 2020. Over 2600 pages complete with summaries of each one including every study cited by their expert. You should

have seen defense counsel's face turn green when I handed him his box. And, for good measure, I flew in Judith Anderson to testify in trial about this science. That's what you have to do. Overwhelm them. You can't wing it, or do what you think is just barely enough. It's all or nothing for us. We have to win by three touchdowns or, since most of you are not in the US, you have to win by 5 goals.

Here is the other thing about little old me taking on this army. This isn't a bar fight that you can't win, with 6 guys beating you with pool cues all at once. This is a legal bar fight, with rules that require the defense to trot out one attorney at a time to do opening, direct cross, and summation. Like the Roman legend of Horatius at the bridge who singlehandedly held off the invading army one soldier at a time, one well prepared lawyer can take on and defeat an army of lawyers.

The end result is that we won everything. The judge ordered them to accept toxic encephalopathy, neurocognitive dysfunction, and two visual impairments, saccadic eye movement and convergence insufficiency. So, let's turn to our two main points.

5 How to Build Your Case

I started out by telling the court that my case had two bookends that we will prove conclusively: this fume event happened and Captain Myers is impaired. In between is the scientific and medical causation. I then described that this causation consisted of four links of a chain, each one forged independently, each one necessary, and each one relying on the other links: the factual link of his fume exposure, the scientific link demonstrating that these fumes can cause these harmful effects, the medical causation link, and the impairment link. These links join together to connect our bookends.

Starting with [the first link, the factual link](#), your presentation is driven by the nature of your client's exposure: was this a fume event like I had to work with, is it gradual exposure over time, or some combination of both. Since I had a dramatic fume event with immediate reporting and obvious symptoms, I went with just the fume event. Perhaps I could have also proven that there was the insidious gradual exposure, and the judge's order suggests that I might have succeeded. However, I didn't need to take that chance, especially since I had such good facts. I had some maintenance records, witness statements and testimony. I thought that was enough. I found out that this wasn't enough during the deposition of Dr. Harrison in San Francisco, when opposing counsel badgered him with questions about the fact that the maintenance records suggested that the APU was the culprit, and yet it wasn't even on during the supposed event. How do we know anything really happened etc., etc., etc. At that point of the litigation I didn't even know what the APU was. I realized that if I don't understand this, how am I going to persuade the judge. That's what led me to consult with Dr. Michaelis and later fly her to Oregon to explain to the court that the APU and the engines share common ductwork which had become soiled by the APU. So, even though the APU was off during the runoff, the air from the engines passed through this contaminated duct work, which led to the fume event. By the time she was done testifying, opposing counsel was left with starting his cross examination by saying to the court, "Well, I guess we know exactly what happened, so let's move on to something else."

[The second link in the chain is the scientific causation link](#). These fumes can and have caused these problems. Provide scientific analysis of where and how the body is attacked from a chemical and psychological standpoint. Prove this through the research and testing that has been done, and of course with live expert testimony. Perhaps the most important thing here is to remember who you are attempting to persuade. I remember that when I took on this case I had a Grade School level understanding of organophosphates. Over the course of dozens of phone calls over many months, Judith Anderson patiently educated me, pointed me to the research and directed me to other experts. There is no way that I could have won this case without her help. Now, if you are in front of a jury, your quest is to break down this complicated science to that Grade School level and, while you are at it, make it interesting and entertaining so they will remember what you are saying. Believe me, if your expert tells a jury that most organophosphate esters are direct inhibitors of AchE, they will have no idea what you are talking about and they will disregard the testimony.

The third link in the chain is the **medical causation link**. Establish that it is medically probable that these fumes caused your client's conditions. Provide clear, cogent and concise testimony that is understandable to your judge or jury. Be sure to eliminate all other potential medical explanations for your client's conditions.

The final link in the chain is the **impairment link**. Be sure to emphasize the objective testing that cannot be faked. We had a pet scan, Dr. Abou Donia's bloodwork, an MRI and a CT scan, visual testing and three separate neuropsychological tests. If you are trying a personal injury case, this is where you finish up with demonstrating the effect these conditions have had on your clients' quality of life and his economic loss.

Those are the four links of the chain that form your case. Each is necessary, each is independent, and yet each relies on the other links.

6 How to Defend the Castle

I think of my case as a castle being attacked. If they breach any wall they can sack your castle and you will lose your case. You have to defend and defeat every attack. The key to success is to anticipate all the possible attacks on your case. That way you and your witnesses can be prepared.

With that in mind, here is what we faced and how we responded, which should give you a pretty good idea what to expect.

6.1 Attacks on the First: The Factual Link

The nature of the attacks on the factual link will depend on the nature of the exposure you are claiming. For a fume event, you should expect that they will argue that this could never happen and it certainly didn't happen here. Your response is to explain how this could ever happen: where the air comes from and how it becomes contaminated. I highly recommend visual art here. This can be a little animated video showing the circulation of air, or something as simple as the hand written drawing that Susan Michaelis prepared for the court in my case. Remember keep it simple, keep it interesting. Your judge or jury has to understand how this could possibly happen.

The other aspect of the factual link is the evidence of your particular fume event. You will want all the relevant maintenance records, which can be tricky because you should expect the airline to minimize their records and then hide what they do have. You have to do more than send out a subpoena and hope. You need to scrounge around and try to uncover the records for yourself. Then, you will want expert testimony explaining (in simple terms) the significance of those records.

For gradual exposure, expect that their experts will say that there IS no gradual exposure, be prepared to counter this with expert testimony and the research papers that have been done that show that there is a gradual exposure to these fumes.

6.2 Attacks on the Second: The Science Link

For the second link, the science link, you can expect several attacks.

6.2.1 The First Attack: Dose Response, Dose Response, Dose Response

Their experts argued that it is impossible, even irresponsible to claim causation without knowing the exact composition of the fumes and the exact amount of every isomer and nano particle, something you of course cannot do. You should prepare your scientists for this line of questioning.

Dr. Harrison effectively refuted this by observing that there was plenty of evidence from which to render an opinion without exact dosage. He is frankly the best expert witness I have ever seen. When asked a the tough question about his ability to render such a causation opinion without knowing exact doses, he actually thought quietly for a full 20

seconds and then said, "I have a five part answer to that question." Opposing counsel sagged into his chair so much I thought he was melting.

You should certainly explain that it is the airlines that are preventing this exactitude by refusing to put air monitors on the planes, and that might make that judge or jury angry. But, it won't win this argument. You need solid affirmative testimony about the ability to render an opinion without knowing the exact dose. In my final summation I used the parable of the dead policeman.

Imagine a burning building. Imagine that the first person on the scene is a policeman. Imagine he hears screams, and he rushes into the building without protective equipment. Imagine he doesn't make it out alive. Imagine that afterwards, his body is found unburned and quiet dead. Imagine that his heirs file a worker's compensation claim which is then denied by the insurance company. Imagine that the same industry expert from Seattle testifies that since we don't know the exact composition of the smoke there is no way to establish causation. Dose response, dose response, dose response. I think that I would be happy to take that case and I'd win that one too.

6.2.2 The Second Predictable Attack: Tri Ortho Isomers and OPIDN

The second predictable attack is their assertion that the only harmful components of the fumes are the tri ortho isomers. Nothing else matters, and the only endpoint to measure is OPIDN (organo phosphate induced delayed neurotoxicity), nothing else matters. This leads to Dr. Jelly Beans, as I call their expert. He is smart, articulate, and quick on his feet, so he is a handful to cross examine. He is also clever, charismatic, handsome and well dressed, so juries love him. Don't underestimate this guy. He is good. His MO is to bring in a jelly bean and a picture of the space needle in Seattle, and then tell the jury that there is SO little ortho content in the oil now that if the total ortho content was represented by this jelly bean, you would have to fill the entire space needle with these jelly beans to develop OPIDN. Great visual. Bad science. There are two fundamental problems with this.

First, the tri ortho-cresyl phosphate isomer is NOT the only harmful component. What about the di ortho and mono ortho, and the meta and para isomers, what about the nano particles that are formed at high temperatures. What about all the other toxins and the evidence that the effects on the body are worse when hit with several toxins at once. I repeatedly referred to these fumes as a primordial soup of toxins. The Mobile Memos from 1988 and 1990 make clear that measuring ToCP alone is not a reliable indicator in light of the many other toxins in the oil. The MSDS sheets for Mobile II reveal that there are many hazards. The cans of oil themselves contain warnings that TCP can cause nerve damage. This is all compelling evidence since it comes from the oil manufacturer.

Second, OPIDN is not the only possible consequence. In fact, it's the least likely. Your scientists need to make this point, and back it up with the research that has been done that shows that there are a wide variety of disabling effects aside from OPIDN. The research done by Dr. Abou Donia, Dr. Van Netten, and Dr. Michaelis provides solid evidence of this.

If you really want to win your case, bring in all three to explain their research. I got two out of three. I just couldn't lure Dr. Van Netten down from Canada. As we heard yesterday, Dr. Howard's paper from 2020 is exactly on point in refuting the industry logic here. In our trial, Dr. Jellybeans switched it up by using M&Ms to represent the total ortho content, saying that you would have to stack them so high as to reach the space station to have a harmful effect. That led me to open up cross by asking him, "Gee, what happened to the jelly beans? Does that have more jury appeal? Do you think that M&Ms are more suitable for a judge?" After about 10 minutes of this, he had about enough of me, but it did serve to knock him off his skates a little, to use an old hockey term.

I asked him if he regularly testified on behalf of the airlines, and he answered by declaring that he had never testified for Jet Blue before. I then I pulled out a couple of big folders filled with lots of paper and pulled out about a hundred pages and asked him if he testified in the trial of blah versus blah because I have the transcript of his testimony right here, and he admitted that he had. I asked if he had in fact testified in several cases, pointing to the stack of papers saying, "I have lots of transcripts here. Do I need to pull them all out?" and he reluctantly answered "yes". He

quickly clarified that he only meant to say that he had not testified for this particular airline, not any airline. This caused the judge to squint at him. I asked if he had ever testified behalf of a pilot that fumes had caused impairment? He said he would never do that because these fumes are harmless. I asked him if his opinion would be different if both pilots had died right there in the cockpit during the fume event and he said no it wouldn't. He would want to know what they had to eat that day. More squinting from the judge.

I then went through a barrage of scientific papers that contradicted his theories: "What about this language in Freudenthal? How do you reconcile your opinion with Houtzager, or the research from Howard and Michaelis?" One by one he admitted not being familiar with them. He has research associates who do the research and then write him memos. He did offer to read them on the witness stand and comment. I told him that it wasn't my job to teach him his job.

Thanks to the banker's box idea, I was able to highlight the extent to which the studies he cited don't really say what he claims they say. I knew from experience that this particular judge is just the type of person who would paw through his box and read it for himself. His 100 page order reflects the fact that he clearly did. For example, their expert testified that he can tell what the maximum possible exposure could ever be in any fume event, citing several studies. My response was that none of papers he cited for this proposition involved measurements taken during an actual fume event. You had lots of measurements taken under normal flight conditions, a few smell events, and one with air samples taken on the tarmac. The 2011 De Nola study he cited looked at 78 samples from military aircraft. None were taken during a fume event and they actually threw out two samples because they deemed the measurements to be too high. If only life was that easy.

In my closing argument I noted that making this assertion is like declaring that you can tell what the maximum possible exposure to smoke would be in a house fire by taking a measurement of the air quality in a house that is not on fire. I also made a point of differentiating between a fume event and a smell event. This comes up in two contexts: first, underreporting of fume events by call them smell events, second by allowing them to claim that research shows no TCP in the air even during a fume event. I explained to the court that a fume event is bad enough to cause a diversion of the flight or requiring medical care. A smell event is when you are sitting next to a passenger with bad flatulence. Since he probably isn't farting out TCP, the air samples will be negative for that.

The discrediting of their witness was successful. The judge stated in his order that this expert was professionally biased (ouch) and that while he certainly was well credentialed, his opinion was riddled with flaws both big and small (ouch).

The most important preparation to effectively cross examine their experts is to read the transcripts of their prior testimony so you know what they are going to say, and look up all the research they cite so that you can demonstrate that it doesn't say what they claim it says.

6.2.3 Another Line of Attack: Fumes are Harmless

Another line of attack you should anticipate comes courtesy of the OSHA regulations that suggest that these fumes are harmless. A little humor and perhaps sarcasm is in order here. I pointed out that these regulations are based on outdated science that attempted to measure how much of this crap a hen has to drink before it falls over paralyzed. I like the comment in one of the research papers that hens are favored over rats as subjects because they fall over nicely when paralyzed.

There are several holes in the science behind these regulations. Hens are not humans, inhalation is worse than ingestion, and there is a lot of harm that can be done short of paralysis. Captain Myers is severely disabled and yet he would be a negative response on this study because he didn't fall over paralyzed.

6.2.4 This Next Attack: Are You a Toxicologist?

This next attack you should expect was beaten like a drum throughout this litigation: “Are you a toxicologist?” The cross examination of every one of our 13 expert witnesses (other than Dr. Abou Donia who is a toxicologist) started with this line of questioning, “Are you a toxicologist? Wouldn’t you agree that this case comes down to the toxicology? Wouldn’t you defer to the toxicologists? And you’re not a toxicologist, are you?” It took me several depositions before I caught on to their strategy.

By doing this, they want to neutralize everyone who is not a toxicologist so the whole case comes down to their toxicologist against whatever toxicologist you have. They think they will win that battle, especially in front of a jury. Chances are, your toxicologist is not professional witnesses like their witness will be. That matters, unfortunately. Just really knowing your stuff doesn’t make you an effective witness. You still have to be able to patiently break the science down to the grade school level for your jury while at the same nimbly dancing around the various traps and snares tossed out there by a good trial attorney. This is where the links of the chain concept comes in handy. I pointed out to the court that opposing counsel spent most of his time belittling the doctors because they are not scientists and the scientists because they are not doctors. They don’t have to be. Each link relies on the other links.

Your scientists don’t need to read thousands of pages of medical records or the maintenance records to render a persuasive opinion. Those are the other links of the chain. Their opinion centers around the scientific plausibility of harmful effects from fumes, assuming that the surrounding factual and medical links are true. The fact that their expert has read the medical record does not make their opinion stronger. Similarly, your doctors do not defer to the toxicologists, and they do not defer to the mechanics. Their opinion by necessity assumes the facts of your case. They were not on the flight deck when this happened. And, they are assuming that this causal connection is scientifically plausible. Don’t let your doctors stumble into defending and explaining the science unless they happen to really know this stuff, which is unlikely. It is better to have them stick to the concept that they are assuming the accuracy of the factual history and assuming the plausibility of the science. Remember, they are not deferring to the “toxicologists”.

At this conference we have listened to some of the brightest minds in the world, people from over two dozen different specialties and fields. According to this industry logic, virtually all of you would have to defer to the industry toxicologist. I think we would all take exception to that notion. Fortunately, the judge in our case did too. This bizarre obsession with toxicology led to the following vignette on day two of my trial. Judith Andersons was our first witness that day. Dr. Susan Michaelis, my wife Helen and several other people were sitting in the back of the courtroom. I began with the good old trial tactic called steeling their thunder. I spent the first 15 minutes of direct examination establishing that Judith was not a toxicologist. We also established that she does, however, have considerable relevant education in chemistry as well as extensive training and firsthand experience investigating fume events that make her eminently qualified as an expert. She also explained that there were many other disciplines, specialties, and degrees that would be highly useful in providing expert testimony. I was also later accused by my wife of having sarcastically mimicked opposing counsel when I asked Judith on direct, “Are you a toxicologist?”

Despite this effort to mock this whole line of questioning, opposing counsel’s very first question was, “Are you a toxicologist?” This produced an audible groan from the back of the room. Then after ten more minutes of beating this very dead horse came yet another question about her lack of toxicological training and there came another, this time, barely perceptible sound from the back of the courtroom leading opposing counsel, with trembling hand, to stop the proceedings and loudly demand that the judge clear the courtroom: “There is chortling going on back there and it’s making it impossible for me to concentrate.” All eyes then turn to the back of the room where Susan and Helen both sat in the corner looking as innocent as possible like the cat that ate the canary. No chortling here, no sirree bob.

Well, the judge said he didn’t hear anything and refused to clear the courtroom (although I suspect he did and he was probably stifling his own chortle) I resisted the temptation of observing that audience will stop chortling when you stop asking stupid questions. I will say that the judge subtly expressed his opinion on this matter when he stated in his order that he considered Judith to also be a toxicologist.

6.3 Attacks on the Third Link: Medical Causation

You should expect the other side to argue that the most harm that can ever come from a fume event is perhaps a little coughing and perhaps a little effect on the peripheral nerves but nothing that ever lasts more than a day or two and certainly nothing that effects the central nervous system. You need your scientists affirm your that these fumes cause much more than that, and your doctors to affirm that the various conditions they are treating have been caused by these fumes. I see a two step process to prove that these fumes can impair the central nervous system.

First, show how these chemicals actually affect the body. Be sure that you bring this science down to the Grade School level for your judge or jury. **Second, bring in the research showing how widespread the reporting of these effects has been worldwide.** The work of Dr. Michaelis in 2016 is useful here.

I used the Rain in July argument here. If the other side asserts that it can never rain in July, the fact that there is evidence that it has rained in July many times before undermines their claim. The fact that hundreds of people have had central nervous system effects undermines their claim of impossibility. However, you can't prove this point with this data alone. You need to have the scientific proof as to how this happens.

6.4 The Final Link: Your Client's Disability

This has its own set of attacks. Is your client really impaired? The basic argument is that since everyone knows that these fumes are harmless, your client's complaints are either the result of some other medical condition, or his is simply faking. You need to defend both possibilities.

First, eliminate all the other potential medical causes. They will say all these conditions are diffuse and can have other explanations. Fine. Eliminate the other explanations. The big battle will over your client's credibility. I brought in several other pilots to testify about how much my client loves flying and would never voluntarily give that up and would never fake anything. You need to do the same. You can also expect massive amounts of surveillance, so this would be a really bad time for your client to take up the unicycle. Both my client and I were followed and harassed. You should expect that and prepare your client for that.

I made sure that my character witnesses were all in uniform, as was my client. I also insisted that he be referred to as Captain Myers throughout the trial. The judge agreed, saying he had earned that, which I took to be an early good sign. We did such a good job of establishing my client's credibility that when the other side made a few half hearted attempts to malign him in their closing argument, I referred to that as throwing Mud on the Mona Lisa in my Rely Argument. Maybe it won't look quite as good, at least until it is wiped off, but it doesn't detract from the intrinsic quality of the painting.

So there you have it, *build your case, defend your castle.*

7 Closing Thoughts

Now, I'd like to close with two thoughts.

My first thought, why are we all really here at this conference? Yes, we have accomplished all of our stated goals for this conference. But what is the real overriding goal. We want safer air to breathe on airplanes for crew and passengers. *The more we can understand this issue and the science, the more we can effectively advocate for and accomplish changes that will bring us that clean air.*

My second thought is that I see three ways that these necessary changes can happen:

1. **Voluntary changes by the airlines.** Sometimes with corporations this really does happen. It isn't always a battle between good and evil. Unfortunately, there are economic factors working against that option. These are expen-

sive changes at a time when Covid has decimated the airline industry. At this point it is still cheaper for them to crush each case that comes along rather than to fix the planes.

2. [Governments can regulate and legislate rules and laws to effect these changes.](#) However, that is a slow process. Regulatory agencies can be unresponsive and often are more concerned about the wellbeing of the companies than their employees. Legislative changes have to overcome powerful lobbies. Nevertheless, there is increasing pressure for change and there is some cause for hope. Eventually.
3. [This leaves the courts and us trial lawyers. We can force changes, and we have done it before.](#) We are the tip of the sword. This one loss to me won't change the airline industry, but the next twenty losses that follow will. *At some point the financial threat of judgments will outweigh the cost of change.* The good old bottom line.

Frankly, I don't care whether they make the changes for the right reasons or the wrong ones. Just make the dang changes. The time is ripe. Think of big tobacco. When I was a kid it was an open question as to whether or not tobacco was harmful. The tobacco institute had some very well credentialed scientists who backed them up. Powerful forces blocked legislation. Smoking was even allowed on planes, which seems crazy now. It's like a public swimming pool that has a peeing section and a non peeing section. Now, it's taken for granted that tobacco in all forms is bad for you. It even says so on the label now. There no longer is a credible argument to the contrary, thanks in part to a flood of successful litigation. However, to start that flood someone had to win that first case.

That's where we are now with cabin air safety. We are right on the cusp of change. We have won that first case. *I have given you the roadmap of how to win the next one.* Soon, the argument that these fumes are harmless will be laughed out of the room like so much tobacco smoke. But it will take winning more cases like mine. I sincerely hope that my case and this talk can help that cause. At some point we will make it more costly for the industry not to make the necessary changes.

But you have to win your cases. There is too much at stake: both the financial well-being of your client, and the health and safety of everyone who flies. You have to care more than they do. You have to leave nothing to chance. You have to prepare your witnesses for the predictable cross examination. Do not underestimate the other side. Know their case better than they even do. Obtain and read transcripts from other trials so you know what their experts will say in advance. Know the research so well that you can rattle it off while you cross examine their witnesses. And above all, make your case and your experts understandable to your judge or jury. You are not trying to win a High School debate. Persuade your judge and jury. And just win the damn case. We are the tip of the sword. And may your edge ever be sharp.

This is Glen Lasken, coming to you from the snowy mountains of Sisters, Oregon.